

TEACHING TURKISH EXAMPLES IN LITERARY EDUCATION IN A COMPARATIVE METHOD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15860407>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 05-Iyul 2025 yil

Ma'qullandi: 07-Iyul 2025 yil

Nashr qilindi: 11-Iyul 2025 yil

KEY WORDS

Modern education, Turkish literature, historical-comparative method, historical biographical method, tradition and identity, educational process, principles of approach..

ABSTRACT

The role of the spiritual and literary heritage created by great figures in the thousand-year history of the Turkic peoples is incomparable. One of the important issues is the study of surviving copies of literary sources created by ancestors of the past, the identification of differences between manuscripts and texts, and the publication of newly discovered information. In the 21st century, with the development of science and technology, there is a need to form noble qualities in the minds of the growing younger generation, to educate them as worthy successors to their ancestors. The harmony of education and upbringing leads to the formation of a harmonious generation. This article examines the ideas regarding the teaching of examples of Turkic literature abroad, in particular, the teaching and learning of the creative heritage of Alisher Navoi abroad. The research work of Uzbek scientists on the teaching of classical works abroad is commented on. The effective aspects of using foreign methods and techniques along with national methodological experiences in the process of literary education are considered. Research on the teaching and learning of Uzbek literature abroad is analyzed.

There are countless great people in the history of the peoples of the East who have left their names forever. Encyclopedists such as Abu Nasr Farobi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi made an incomparable contribution to the development of science and technology. Word artists such as Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Mirzo Muhammad Haydar, Hasankhodja Nisari, Sharafiddin Raqimi developed the field of art and literature. The spiritual monuments created by these people, who knew the value of words, embodied the issue of human perfection. If the growing generation looks at the sources of the past with deep respect and reverence, the Uzbek people will continue to educate great people such as Amir Temur and **Jalaluddin** Manguberdi. The names of kings and princes, sultans and emirs who supported the great thinkers and masters of the word who contributed to the civilization of the Turkic peoples will live forever.

Literature educates the feelings and emotions of a person, distinguishes him from other beings due to the evolutions in the spiritual world. Since the creation-beginning of the world is due to "Word", its end is also due to it. Therefore, a reader familiar with fiction is distinguished from others by the richness of his literary-aesthetic world. The reader's worldview, thinking and feelings are enriched through constant reading and study. Love and thirst for the word complement the reader's intellectual level. From the past to the present, human civilization has been progressing as a result of acquiring knowledge and mastering crafts. Studying classical sources, systematically rereading, memorizing, and working with dictionaries familiarize the modern reader with history and great figures. It creates an opportunity to understand the fundamental essence of the masterpieces of advice and wisdom that lie at the heart of the spiritual heritage left by our ancestors. Research conducted and ongoing in the field of teaching Uzbek literature shows that the history of Uzbek literature has been studied by literary critics and methodologists, fundamental research on specific issues has been carried out, and treatises, manuals, and monographs have been published. "The reason why literature teaching deserves special attention is that it is not only a means of imparting knowledge, but, first of all, is aimed at shaping the spirituality of the younger generation. The use of classical literature in the formation of students' spirituality through lessons and extracurricular activities has a special place. Because the layers of our national spirituality have been shaped, first of all, by the examples of our centuries-old literature. Islamic spirituality, which has been subject to many restrictions due to secular ideology, has been clearly manifested in our classical literature" [Yo'ldoshev, 2019: 10].

Today, fundamental reforms and innovations are being observed in the education systems of the nations of the world. The rapid development of science and technology requires improving the quality of education, encouraging students to think creatively in the process of mastering the subject, and being able to apply their knowledge, skills and qualifications in practice. Awareness of computer technologies and thorough mastery of foreign languages make it possible to introduce new methods and technologies in literature education.

Foreign studies of the life and work of the great poet Alisher Navoi, the king and poet Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, as well as the study of the history of Uzbek literature by foreign scholars, show that today it is necessary to enrich the literary education process with modern approaches and use interdisciplinary integration in literature lessons so that young people can easily and conveniently master national models.

Serious reforms are being carried out in our country in the socio-political, spiritual and educational spheres. As on all fronts, significant changes are taking place in science, in particular, in the study of the history of our national literature, and in the promotion of unique written sources that are our spiritual and cultural monuments. The historic resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on October 19, 2020 on the widespread celebration of the "580th anniversary of the birth of the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi" also set important tasks in the field. In particular, the II Republican Scientific and Practical Conference on "Theoretical and Source Foundations of the Study of Uzbek Classical Literature", held on October 22, 2020, is an important continuation of the work carried out towards these tasks.

Today, there is a need to organize the literary education process on the basis of innovative technologies, to resort to foreign teaching methods based on the experience of national methodologies. Based on this need, the appropriate use of interactive and innovative methods that help increase the knowledge and potential of students in literature lessons contributes to the correct organization of the lesson from a scientific, theoretical, methodological point of view. The culture and literature of the Turkic peoples are closely related to each other

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